

TEACHING ADOLESCENT LEARNERS IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE AT SCHOOL

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Abstract. This article focuses on the problem of teaching English to adolescents. Teaching is an important process for passing on knowledge, but it can be difficult at times depending on the age level. Teenagers differ from other learners in that they are thought to be the most disobedient and discouraged from learning. Adolescence is a tough period in a child's life when many psychological and physical changes occur. As a result, in order to operate effectively, teachers must become acquainted with these developments. There are numerous effective and efficient strategies that teachers can incorporate into their classes to boost students' understanding and overall comprehension.

Keywords: English, teaching, age level, Teenagers, teachers, strategies, result.

ОБУЧЕНИЕ ПОДРОСТКОВ АНГЛИЙСКОМУ ЯЗЫКУ В ШКОЛЕ

Аннотация. Данная статья посвящена проблеме преподавания английского языка подросткам. Преподавание — важный процесс передачи знаний, но иногда это может быть сложно в зависимости от возраста. Подростки отличаются от других учащихся тем, что их считают самыми непослушными и отталкивающими от обучения. Подростковый возраст — сложный период в жизни ребенка, когда происходит много психологических и физических изменений. В результате, чтобы работать эффективно, учителя должны быть ознакомлены с этими разработками. Существует множество эффективных и действенных стратегий, которые учителя могут использовать в своих классах, чтобы улучшить понимание учащимися и общее понимание.

Ключевые слова: Английский язык, преподавание, возрастной уровень, подростки, учителя, стратегии, результат.

The first chapter of this article defines the term "teaching" and gives a general explanation of teaching approaches. The methods are separated into conventional and unorthodox methods, and their most common tactics and goals are discussed.

The second chapter provides a basic characterisation of adolescents as well as a description of adolescents as English language learners. The teacher should be familiar with the features of the adolescent learner so that he can act appropriately and deal with any problems that may arise during the learning process. Furthermore, correct learner classification will make this process easier and will show the teacher the best approaches to collaborate with the student. This chapter also explains the various learning styles and tactics used in the language learning process.

The third chapter is dedicated to the methods used for teaching English to adolescents, taking into account the learners' exact age and needs. This chapter also discusses the most beneficial learning types and learning practices that will assist the student in becoming the most effective.

CHAPTER ONE

Teaching English

The didactic process in which both the teacher and the student participate is called teaching. Teaching, according to Johnsson-Walker (1828), implies instructing and informing as a

master. Teaching is defined by Kimble—Garnezy (1963:133) as "showing or assisting someone to learn how to do something, giving instructions, directing in the study of anything, supplying knowledge, causing to know or comprehend something." Brown (2000) proposes that the term "teaching" be replaced with the term "learning," because "teaching" supports the learning process, provides the learner with opportunities to learn, and creates the conditions necessary for learning. A broader notion of teaching always leads to a plethora of approaches that the teacher might employ to ease the learning process. **Direct methods** are considered to be traditional methods, although they can be found in the classroom on a daily basis. According to Komorowska (2001), the **Grammar Translation Method** is the oldest and most traditional method of teaching foreign language. This method focuses on understanding grammar rules and applying them to the translation of foreign language materials. The primary purpose of this method is for the student to achieve communicative competence. **The Audio - Lingual Method** shares many characteristics with the **Direct Method** and "was solidly anchored in linguistics and psychological philosophy" (Brown, 2000:23). The target language is not used, which has a significant impact on speaking. **Cognitive Code Learning** also aids in the development of all four students' talents, including not only speaking but also writing, grammar, and reading comprehension.

According to Komorowska (2001), there are numerous similar characteristics that may characterize all unorthodox approaches. The teacher's commands in the imperative form, bodily response, and listening are more crucial than oral production in this method. It is critical in **Total Physical Response (TPR)** to make learning enjoyable rather than stressful. Students' blunders are seen as ordinary aspects that always emerge during educational progress in Silent Way. The next method, **Community Language Learning** (also known as Counseling Language Learning), implies that people communicate only when they want to exchange information on a certain subject. Reading and writing are practiced as technical skills based on what the students have already learned. Brown's method enables the teacher to test the students in a friendly and non-stressful manner. Students are encouraged to express their emotions and share their views, but they are not pushed to talk if they are uncomfortable. Komorowska (2001) mentions **Suggestopedia** as another innovative way. The fundamental goal of **Suggestopedia** is to persuade them that they are mistaken by generating scenarios that will aid in language development.

CHAPTER TWO

Characteristics of adolescents

Adolescence represents the teenage years between the ages of 13 and 19. This is a period of physical, emotional, and moral growth. According to Maier (2011), several significant changes occur in the lives of young people throughout this period. Adolescents begin to socialize with their peers rather than their parents. Peer groups serve as a transitory point of reference for building a sense of identity. Maier (2011) also believes that emotional shifts are a major influence in adolescent traits. Adolescence is a time when teens experience an "emotional maelstrom." Another important feature to discuss is sociability. Adolescents begin to socialize with their peers rather than their parents. Peer groups, according to Bishop and Inderbitzen (1995), provide a variety of critical purposes during adolescence, including providing a transitory reference point for a developing sense of identity. "Anyone who has taught secondary school children has experienced lessons, even days and weeks, when the task looked impossible,

if not hopeless." However, if, as methodologist Penny Ur indicates, teenage pupils are the best language learners overall" (Harmer, 2001: 38).

Teenagers have a reputation for being the most challenging learners, as Ur (1996) observed. Although their potential is greater than that of young children, they appear to lack drive, are less receptive to instructor encouragement, and are difficult to supervise. It takes time for the teacher to acquire the students' trust and respect. "Anyone who has taught secondary school children has experienced lessons, even days and weeks, when the task looked impossible, if not hopeless." However, if, as methodologist Penny Ur indicates, teenage pupils are the best language learners overall" (Harmer, 2001: 38).

Parents and teachers may notice aggressive conduct as well as some discipline issues. Adolescents experience irritability and mood changes. As their curiosity and eagerness to explore grows, they turn to illegal substances like cigarettes and alcohol.

CHAPTER THREE

Adolescent English learning strategies and teaching methods

Adolescents are a tough group of students that must be taught in a systematic manner. **The Direct Method** and **Counseling Language Learning** appear to be effective approaches for teaching English to teenagers. Students should be able to apply language in real-world circumstances during lessons. Students can use **the Direct Method** to generate questions and answers in a foreign language. **Counselling Language Learning (CLL)** allows pupils to work as a group rather than individually. Adolescents are very close to their peers, and this strategy allows them to build a community. In the first stage, students select a topic and pick what they want to discuss. They tell the teacher in their mother tongue what they want to say, and the tutor offers them prepared English pieces. A typical lesson, which is conducted by means of **CLL** has five stages and they can be compared to the evolution from the childhood to the adulthood. "In order for any learning to take place (...) what is first needed is for the members to interact in an interpersonal relationship in which students and teacher join together to facilitate learning in a context of valuing and prizing each individual in the group" (Brown, 1994: 59).

Reflection is the first stage. Students can sit in a circle to create a community atmosphere. The pupils deliberate in quiet before deciding what to discuss. Outside the circle, the teacher stands. If our kids don't have many ideas, they can do some brainstorming. The talk is then recorded in the second stage. After selecting a topic, pupils tell the teacher in their home tongue what they want to say, and the tutor provides prepared segments in English. The third stage is discussion and debate. The students discuss their reactions to the recorded conversation, as well as their feelings and attitudes. Transcription is involved in the fourth stage. Students are listening to and transcribing the recording. When pupils ask for assistance, the teacher steps in. The final stage is to analyze. This entails examining the tenses and terminology and explaining why they were chosen. Students are fully engaged in the process at this point, and they can choose which portion of the process to evaluate.

When used wisely, **the Grammar Translation Method** is a useful tool, but it should be utilized with caution. A grammatical syllabus appeals to certain types of learners because it provides them with a clear set of objectives and a sense of accomplishment. Others prefer to use their mother tongue and compare grammatical structures to their first language equivalents. "Translation seems to be a useful tool if used sparingly, but it should be used with caution." (Harmer, 1993:86). If the teacher uses definitions and pictures to illustrate the meanings of

lexical items, it takes a long time. “Sometimes it is worth giving the mother tongue equivalent rather than to pending valuable time trying to define or show the meaning. It is of great value when no easy alternative suggests itself or highlight the danger of false cognates.” (Harmer, 1993:86).

The process of teaching the rules of a language must enable pupils to accurately express their opinions and grasp the comments directed at them by the teacher. Grammar students in GTM will be able to convert even tough texts from their original language into English. The benefit of GTM is that by the time students graduate from college, they will be able to regulate language tools such as vocabulary and grammar, as well as understand texts in a variety of contexts.

Students are the most effective learners when taking into consideration their personal learning style. There are many tests available to help teachers discover which is best learning style for his learners. We should consider the three types in term of modality mentioned by Komorowska (2001). In general, if there is someone in the classroom who is more likely to think in pictures, prefers to meet with someone in person, and is more likely to want visual diagrams when completing a project, the learner has visual learning tendencies. Similarly, auditory learners prefer to think in terms of sounds, prefer to talk on the phone, and prefer verbal instructions. Finally, kinesthetic learners think in terms of moving visuals, prefer to participate in an activity by chatting with someone, and tend to leap right into a project without reading directions.

The functions of strategies help students to access information from memory, make connections between what they know and what they are learning. Strategies must be explicitly taught to help students help themselves. Using social strategies in foreign language learning is quite efficient and allow the students to be more self-confident in English.

In conclusion, an attempt was undertaking to show how challenging matter is teaching English to adolescents. It is strongly related to the fact that adolescents go through a very stormy period, including significant psychological and physical transformations. The teacher has an important role to play because he is responsible for making the students to learn in a best way.

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